

BM-5102 Organizational Behaviour

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Introduction

My name is Muhammad Abdul Muhshi Bin Awang Adam, I am currently taking masters in management at the University of Brunei Darussalam with the registration number of 20M1285. Intrinsically the main motivation why I am taking masters is to further my study and to be productive in society and socialize with my peers, and extrinsically the monetary reward given in terms of university allowances. My goal after taking my master is to be a clerk however in order to achieve that goal I need to measure my requirement in terms of skills and capability as there is a mismatch of employer expectation and employee aspiration in Brunei Darussalam (Musa & Idris,2020).

This is my first semester and for this semester I am taking an easy approach for my University life by taking only four modules. The modules I have been taking were Organizational behaviour, research methodology, Accounting and financial management and management theories and practices. This paper is a self critique on what I have done on one of the modules which is **Organizational behaviour**.

Because of covid-19 the method of learning in the year 2020 is a little bit different than the previous years, for the first half of the semester Brunei Darussalam was still under a strict social distancing protocol there the classes was conducted online however as Brunei Darussalam lifted the protocol stage by stages the classes were slowly conducted face to face. In organizational behaviour we were assigned two reports which is an individual report and group report therefore both of the progress and my sentiment of towards both will be provided below starting from the group report

Group report

For the group report, There were four members in my group Hazirah,Zakiyamani,Widad and me. Initially Zakiyamani was not our group member but we have another person in the group however after a few weeks people started to drop off from the course possibly from being overwhelmed by the workload or they have found a job. Zakiyamani's group and our group started to merge, the merge is gratefully accepted since Widad and Zakiyamani have known each other however at this time I noticed that my contribution in the group has become less. The topic for our report is The impact of COVID-19 to the trust,morale and organizational commitment for pilots, this topic was chosen by Widad, at first I was concerned on how are we going to collect data and I expressed it to her she replied that she has connections with the pilots therefore at that time it was assumed that the data collection will be progressing swiftly thus everyone unanimously agreed with her including me.

The duration for the report was supposed to be from August until the 20th october and every week we have a set of goals and submission to be completed, everything was going well until around the middle of october when there is a change in protocol in ethique form for the report thus made the due date extended until the seventh of November. The change of protocol in the ethique form made the report progress halted. This is because in order to collect data we were required to fill in an ethique form without it we are not allowed to use and collect data. The

change in protocol made our group demotivated as it comes at the later half of the semester and we have already contacted the participant for our data collection.

We were given the option to use another method of data gathering which is systematic literature review by our lecturer. However, Widad managed to get permission and we were allowed to gather data normally. The data was gathered by interviewing the participants and the interview questions were designed by all of us. Since we are lacking time and coordinating with the participant for a one on one interview is practically impossible, we have to conduct the interview in a group setting, the participant was divided into two groups: the senior officer and first senior officers and captain. For the first interview it was conducted by Widad alone and the second interview was conducted by Widad, Zakiyamani and me. However during the second interview I wasn't contributing anything as it seems like they are already established rapport and I felt left out therefore I just tried to help in terms of logistics. The data was then transcribed by all of us but most of the data was transcribed by Hazirah. I really felt grateful to her as she stayed until 3 in the morning to complete the transcribing of the first interview. After getting all the data required to do the report we managed to complete the report within five days. I could say everything in my group is working well, everyone contributed well although I felt that Widad and Hazirah have made most of the contribution. The thing I really like about this group is that everyone is really friendly to each other and every time a task is completed we congratulate and thank each other. If I have the chances to be in the same group with them again in the future I would gladly join them.

Individual report

For the individual report duration was from August until 15th november. The topic for my individual report was firstly "the personality traits and skills required in the entrance level job", I chose this topic because I believe that my research could help people that are new in the employment market to prepare themselves before entering it, however after a consultation with my lecturer it was later change into "the personality traits and skills required in the entrance level job, a case study of two fast casual restaurant" because with this my research will be more specific. This change in title is required as I only have a limited time to do my research and I need to specify my research as much as possible even though at the cost of the data I have collected before the consultation.

In order to collect data required I have designed an interview and approached a few fast casual restaurants, Sugarbun and Easyway and cafe. Both of them give consent for me to conduct an interview for the data required and I even managed to interview Easyway and cafe, however just after a few day I did that my lecturer break a bad news to us that there is a change in protocol and those who didn't managed to get an approval for their ethique form are not allowed to use the data, unluckily I just sent my ethique forms four days before that thus rendered my application unsuccessful. This news demoralized me badly as all the progress I had made halted just like that.

The only option given for us in order to continue our research is by using a systematic literature review. It was the first time I had come across that method at that time, luckily our lecturer has given us enough samples in order for me to learn the method and proceed. And in order to

proceed with my report I have to change back the title into “the personality traits and skills required in the entrance level job” to make it more generalized as I am now using secondary data sources. Although I can say my report is fairly decent and I am quite satisfied with the result, to me there are more things I can do with primary data sources.

Group Reflection

To reflect on what I have done above theoretically I believe what made my group report successful was our teamwork capabilities. Teamwork has played a vital role in order for us to achieve our goal especially in order to overcome the hurdle of changes and increase our performance (Schmutz & Meier & Manser,2019). Other than that what makes the report successful was our group communication. Effective communication allow us to be able to deliver information between each others and when the changes comes we have managed to discuss on what step we should take next even when the change is not mentioned yet, the way we communicate is helping us on which part is lacking and needed to be fix in short communication is a vital foundation for people in order to achieve goals (Iloafu,2017).

Lastly what made our group report successful was the positive reinforcement we gave to each other, whenever one of us accomplished a task or gave out any information regarding the reports we would thanks and reward each other with praises. It is well known that positive reinforcement will increase the motivation level of people especially in a group setting (Diedrich,2010). Although it can be debated that the positive reinforcement could work depending on the people according to theory X and theory Y , people in theory Y would expect more indirect rewards such as acknowledgement and praises in order to better themself and in theory X the main motivation factors is the monetary reward (Zendage,2016)

Individual Reflection

From doing both of the individual and group report I have found out that my personality trait in the term of openness can be considered low, especially when Widad choose a new topic that I considered out of my comfort zone I was doubting a little on my capability to finish the task and when my lecturer told me to change the method of data gathering from interview into systematic literature review which is also new to me I was a bit demoralized as the big five theory dictated that people with low openness are afraid of changes and resists new ideas (Cherry,2020).

What I learned

From taking organizational Behaviour I have learned quite a lot either directly in the class or indirectly. Most of the classes in organizational behaviour touches about motivation and leadership. Other than theories I believe the thing I really appreciate learning is the art of negotiation in class in terms of negotiation between students and the lecturer. When the news of the change of protocol was given out the lecturer tried to negotiate with us in terms of how the the report should be proceeded instead of just giving us a totally a new assignment in return I have observed the act of negotiation from my groupmate Widad in which she indirectly asked for the extension of the group report project. Other than that I could say I learned the importance of

having a timeline when doing an assignment as it would myself to be more organized and know if my projects are achievable or not.

What I would do differently

If I can reverse time within this semester I would do more things differently, firstly I would start doing a log book so I could track what I have done and learned within this semester. it could also serve as a memoir of my master of management journey. Secondly on behalf of both of the reports I would do the ethique form as soon as possible as the news of its requirement only comes to us after the semester break and during our bachelor of degree we are not required to fill it thus we did not know about it until it is too late. Lastly I would create my own timeline as meeting the expected timeline is not enough, therefore there is a requirement for me to exceed the timeline as there needs to be a contingency plan because other modules would affect the initial timeline.

Use of reflective report

This reflective report will be my benchmark in order to do better during my next semester. I will always reflect on this and see how much I have grown within my master of management course.

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